

Life Cycle Assessment of Up-flow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket Microfiltration Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor

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Abstract

Due to the slaughtering process and cleaning of equipment and floors, a large amount of wastewater is produced in slaughterhouses. The potential for nutrient recovery from this wastewater is high. Up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket microfiltration osmotic membrane bioreactors as an innovative treatment technology (UASB MF-OMBRs) provides resource recovery as well as a high level of treatment. In this study, the life cycle assessment (LCA) analysis was carried out for the treatment and resource recovery of slaughterhouse wastewater (SWW) using an UASB MF-OMBR. The results emphasized the significance of the LCA approach to support decision-making when considering possible scenarios for wastewater treatment and resource recovery.

Keywords

LCA; struvite recovery; UASB MF-OMBR; wastewater treatment

INTRODUCTION

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a scientific approach used to assess the potential environmental impacts of products or processes from cradle to grave/gate (Hauschild et al., 2018). LCA presents the opportunity to evaluate the environmental impacts of treating various wastewater kinds with different treatment technologies (Teo et al., 2023). In the literature, there are a lot of LCA studies on the environmental impacts of wastewater treatment technologies, treating generally domestic or municipal wastewater. However, limited LCA studies were conducted on the treatment slaughterhouse wastewater (SWW) while there is no study on its resource recovery with LCA. These LCA studies considered the treatment of SWW with different treatment technologies such as anaerobic digestion (Wang et al., 2021), ultrafiltration (UF) (etinkaya and Bilgili, 2022), and a combination of coagulation, flocculation, dissolved air flotation, membrane bioreactor (MBR), and advanced oxidation processes (AOP) (Teo et al., 2023). Nevertheless, no LCA study has been found on the environmental impacts of SWW treatment and resource recovery with up-flow anaerobic sludge blanket microfiltration osmotic membrane bioreactors (UASB MF-OMBRs).

UASB MF-OMBR systems were developed to increase flux and methane production by reducing the membrane fouling and the effect of salt inhibition on microbial activity (Chang et al., 2019; Hasanoglu et al., 2024). These systems also have resource recovery applications, e.g., struvite recovery from the microfiltration (MF) permeate. The study aims to determine the environmental impacts of a full-scale UASB MF-OMBR system treating SWW.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study assesses the environmental impacts of an UASB MF-OMBR system treating the SWW. A full-scale UASB MF-OMBR system was designed based on the experimental results of a laboratory-scale UASB MF-OMBR system. The functional unit was chosen as 1 m³ treated wastewater. The system boundary starts with the SWW influent and goes through a pretreatment, UASB MF-OMBR, and post treatment process (reverse osmosis, RO). A combined heat and power (CHP) unit, where the produced biogas was combusted, and the struvite as obtained product for resource recovery were also included in the system boundary. The system boundary of the LCA study is given in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. System boundary for the LCA analysis.

Data was collected during the one-year operation of the laboratory-scale UASB MF-OMBR system (Özçelep et al., 2023). In addition to the data obtained from the laboratory-scale UASB MF-OMBR system, the data from the published literature, manufacturer's documents, and Ecoinvent database (v.3) were used. The LCA analysis was performed using the SimaPro 9.1.1.7 software.

In the life cycle impact assessment phase, based on the collected data, the environmental impacts were calculated using the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint H methodology for the following 18 impact categories: fossil resources (FR), mineral resources (MR), tropospheric ozone formation (human) (OF-H), tropospheric ozone formation (eco) (OF-E), stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD), global warming (GW), particulate matter (PM), ionizing radiation (IR), human toxicity (cancer) (HCT), human toxicity (noncancer) (HNCT), water use (WU), freshwater ecotoxicity (FET), freshwater eutrophication (FE), terrestrial ecotoxicity (TET), terrestrial acidification (TA), land use (LU), marine ecotoxicity (MET), and marine eutrophication (ME).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the environmental impacts of a full-scale UASB MF-OMBR plant were investigated by LCA methodology. Fig. 2 illustrates the LCA results for all midpoint categories using the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint H methodology. The results showed that the treatment step, including pre-treatment and the UASB MF-OMBR system, had lower environmental impacts than that of the RO membrane process. Environmental impacts were especially low for SOD, GW, and TA in the treatment step. It was thought that this could be due to the positive environmental impact of the produced biogas and electricity production via CHP. On the other hand, higher environmental loads were seen in the impact categories of FE and ME for the treatment step. It has been reported in the literature that the discharge

of treated wastewater into freshwater contributes to eutrophication through the nutrients in the wastewater (Pretel et al., 2016). In the RO membrane process, the addition of chemicals for struvite precipitation was considered to cause significant environmental impacts, thereby limiting the potential benefits of offsetting struvite production.

Figure 2. Environmental impact of the system.

The results indicated that significant environmental benefits can be achieved through energy recovery from biogas. Moreover, the study highlighted that the nutrient recovery is crucial for mitigating the negative environmental impacts, particularly by reducing the eutrophication potential associated with the nutrient-rich effluents. Thus, future studies on the LCA studies by including the recovery of MF and forward osmosis (FO) permeates of the UASB MF-OMBR as liquid fertilizer or agricultural irrigation water are recommended.

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